

PRESERVATION.EXE: WORKING WITH ICT IN DIGITAL PRESERVATION

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Abstract - Many of us in the field of digital preservation encounter challenges when processing digital carriers and using obsolete or crowdsourced software. Establishing a good relationship with Information and Communications Technology (ICT) services is essential in many cases, but is not always an easy relationship to maintain. This panel delves into the diverse experiences of building such relationships across various institutions, highlighting both the successes and hurdles. Panelists will share insights into navigating institutional policies, addressing cybersecurity concerns, and overcoming ICT skepticism about unconventional practices required for preservation work.

Submission Type - Panel

Keywords - Forensics, storage media, management, software, workflows

Conference Topics - Haerenga - Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

The work of digital preservation is intrinsically tied to the availability of specialised equipment, software tools, and hardware. However, the feasibility of using these resources often depends heavily on the institution's infrastructure and its relationship with ICT services [1]. From navigating stringent cybersecurity protocols to sourcing obsolete hardware, practitioners face numerous challenges that test their technical, logistical, and diplomatic skills.

Furthermore, as laws surrounding data protection, intellectual property, and digital security grow increasingly complex, the stakes for mishandling digital content have never been higher. These pressures are further compounded by the necessity of accessing tools that ICT teams may deem unsafe - such as unsupported operating

systems and software applications, or community-developed open-source software.

Although these issues are occasionally mentioned during conferences and meetings, there has been no dedicated panel to address them comprehensively. This session seeks to address this gap through dialogue and sharing solutions and tips for tackling these challenges within a variety of institutional frameworks.

II. PROPOSED TOPICS

Sourcing Obsolete Hardware - Digital preservation often requires using obsolete hardware that may have been out of production for years and is no longer supported by manufacturers. Panellists will discuss creating solutions to acquiring legacy equipment, such as using online marketplaces, working with donors, or acquiring parts from archives. The discussion will also cover the challenges of maintaining and repairing this equipment, and how to address concerns from ICT teams about using outdated technology.

Leveraging Open-Source and Community-Built Tools - Many preservation tasks rely on tools developed by open-source communities. While these tools are indispensable for working with some of the more obscure or proprietary formats, their unofficial status can make ICT teams and institutions wary. This topic will delve into how practitioners navigate these conversations, ensure the safety of these tools, and demonstrate their value in enabling the recovery and preservation of otherwise inaccessible digital materials.

Cybersecurity and Risk Management - The software and hardware requirements for digital collecting and preservation activities are complex and extend beyond standard operating environments (SOE). Plugging in old digital carriers poses a host of security risks, from malware to corrupted files. This topic will explore how institutions balance the need to access these materials with the necessity of protecting their broader digital ecosystems. Panellists will share methods on collaborating with ICT teams to make these workflows possible.

Institutional Policies and Practices - The division of authority and responsibilities between digital collections management and ICT delivery teams remains contentious. The panel will share

their experiences of communicating the unique needs of digital collections, as compared to the user files and business records ICT teams are more used to dealing with. Panellists will also discuss institutional ICT policies and strategies for aligning them with preservation needs.

Legislative Context and Constraints - Those policies and practices depend on a complex legal landscape that both constrains and empowers the work of digital preservation. These regulations vary between different countries, increasing the barriers to collaboration such as building shared libraries of the software and environments our collections depend on. From copyright restrictions to data protection laws, this topic will address how practitioners navigate these legal constraints while ensuring that preservation work remains compliant and effective.

III. PANELLISTS

Leontien Talboom works as the Technical Analyst at Cambridge University Library. As part of this job she looks after the Transfer Service. This service transfers material from storage media, including floppy disks, hard drives and optical discs.

Andrew Jackson is the Preservation Registries Technical Architect at the Digital Preservation Coalition. His work builds on his research and operational experience with sustainable technologies, with a focus on linking communities of practice through the critical shared resources digital preservation depends on.

Matthew P. Burgess is the Lead Digital Archivist at the State Library of NSW, where he manages the Digital Preservation Lab and the Digital Curation team. He has collaborated with his ICT colleagues for more than eight years to support the essential activities required for long-term preservation of born-digital collections.

Cynde Moya is Director of Prof Melanie Swalwell's Digital Preservation Lab in the Centre of Transformative Media Technologies at Swinburne University of Technology, Melbourne Australia.

1. IV. PANEL SUMMARY

The 90-minute panel session, chaired by William Kilbride of the Digital Preservation Coalition, was structured around four key questions that aimed to

address the proposed topics and invite audience participation from the beginning.

Panellist introductions prompted an initial discussion on securing and managing digital preservation lab spaces. Several panellists noted that their labs were established in small rooms that were not ideal for their growing needs. However, acquiring any dedicated space was suggested as a good starting point.

A. How have relationships between IT departments and digital preservation teams evolved over time?

Panellists provided contrasting examples where relationships have shifted from suspicion or strict control to more collaborative partnerships. Increasing cybersecurity requirements were highlighted as a new complexity, often resulting in increased restrictions and reduced autonomy for digital preservation staff. Examples included the loss of administrative privileges and the implementation of software 'allow-lists'.

However, the panel also recognized that cybersecurity concerns must be balanced against the risks to digital collection management and access that arise through these restrictions. It is important to make it clear that these are collection items (not personal or corporate files) and that these needs arise from the purpose, remit and potentially legal responsibilities of the institution.

The panel emphasised that, wherever possible, we should start by being clear about our needs rather than leading with solutions, and be prepared to adapt our approaches to those established and preferred by ICT colleagues. This includes positively engaging with software 'allow-lists', working with more familiar vendors, or requesting sandboxed environments (e.g. virtual machines, or VLANs - Virtual Local Area Networks) to isolate unsupported operations. 'Shadow IT' (where staff use unsupported software or hardware without seeking permission first) was also highlighted as a widespread tactic, but also a potentially risky approach depending on the context.

Trust-building, regular communication and clear boundaries, roles and responsibilities were highlighted as essential to improve relationships between IT and digital preservation teams. Advocacy and clear communication of archival or collection management requirements were emphasised as

vital for achieving workable solutions. Where possible, the results of these discussions should be codified as institutional policies. This helps maintain agreement on contentious issues such as handling viruses.

B. How can procurement processes adapt to the unique needs of digital preservation, such as sourcing obsolete hardware, while staying within institutional and legal frameworks?

The panel highlighted the incompatibility between standard procurement systems and the realities of acquiring obsolete media, vintage computers, and legacy peripherals. Traditional procurement frameworks assume contemporary suppliers, repeatable supply chains, and the ability to secure multiple competitive quotes. By contrast, digital preservation work often requires purchasing one-off items from online auction sites, where equipment appears unpredictably and may be available only once. Several panellists described negotiations with procurement offices to find more flexible arrangements, such as low-value purchasing exemptions that allow staff to buy directly from platforms like eBay without multiple quotations. Leveraging precedents set by digitisation departments was also highlighted as a potential workaround.

Clarity over long-term asset and ownership was also raised as an important issue, particularly in the context of a project working to share hardware among multiple partners. Institutional accounting requires any financial assets to be recorded and depreciated over time, but the application and details of this are dependent on the context.

These conversations frequently required explaining not only why such items were necessary, but also why they may not function on arrival and may need to be replaced, repaired, or used for parts. The panel also noted the importance of making clear that obsolete equipment is not expected to be supported by IT nor connected to managed institutional networks, helping alleviate concerns about long-term responsibility.

Open-source software procurement introduced additional complexity, but some institutions had successfully procured development services to

enhance existing tools rather than procuring a standalone commercial product.

Electrical safety, compliance testing, and the insurance status of obsolete hardware were recognised as further complications that institutions often overlook. One audience member mentioned that they had successfully advocated for their own staff training to allow them to carry out electrical safety testing and manage this risk directly. Another audience question led to a discussion that made it clear that obsolete hardware is often uninsured, and that the meaningful valuation and assessment of this critical equipment should be addressed in the future. For example, ICT departments may be used to treating obsolete hardware as disposable waste, not valuable and crucial items that enable digital preservation.

C. How can institutions manage the use of outdated, obsolete, open-source, or self-written software that's essential to digital preservation work — while aligning with IT policies on authorised and secure software?

The panel acknowledged that digital preservation work routinely requires software and operating systems that fall outside institutional standard operating environments. Running Windows XP, using emulators, or installing specialist disk imaging tools may be necessary to process collection material, yet these practices often conflict with strict security frameworks. Several institutions rely on isolated or air-gapped machines, sometimes placed on separate VLANs, to permit the use of unapproved software while containing risk. Others make use of virtual machines or sandbox environments for testing tools before approaching IT with a more informed and well-justified case.

Cloud-based emulation environments, such as Emulation as a Service Infrastructure (EAASI), offer a solution by allowing staff to run legacy operating systems via a web browser rather than installing them locally. However, these 'distant' platforms are currently better suited to access and experimentation rather than day-to-day processing, meaning they cannot fully replace the need for older systems in preservation workflows.

The discussion also encompassed legal frameworks, such as copyright exceptions, that allow institutions

to operate older software for preservation purposes. For example, in Australia, the relevant legislation allows purchased software to be used remotely. Purchasing/formal acquisition of software was often preceded by a phase of experimentation of the software options in a less formal or isolated context. One or two larger institutions have successfully worked with software publishers like Microsoft for permission to emulate legacy software, but it was recognised that this advocacy burden was too great for smaller institutions.

Some panellists highlighted that gender and age-related dynamics, in addition to professional hierarchies, can affect how ICT departments respond to requests. Expertise in working with technology can be undervalued or dismissed during initial contact. Where progress was made, it was usually supported by strong managerial advocacy, clear articulation of institutional obligations to provide access to collections, and demonstrating an understanding of and experience working with hardware and software.

D. How can the digital preservation community itself share knowledge, policies, and practical solutions to common IT-related challenges?

The panel emphasised the central role of documentation and knowledge sharing within the community. Case studies, workflow descriptions, procurement examples, advocacy strategies and transparent accounts of both successes and failures were all seen as valuable tools for helping others advocate within their own organisations. Several panellists cited instances where documentation from peer institutions had directly influenced internal decision making, lending authority to arguments that might otherwise be dismissed as niche or exceptional.

Importantly, the panel encouraged the community to document not only challenges but also positive examples of collaboration, helping shift the narrative toward partnership rather than conflict. An example was provided from the Digital Preservation Network for National and State Libraries Australasia (NSLA), which addressed the challenges posed by increasing cybersecurity requirements by creating a briefing paper featuring case studies of successful collaborations between ICT and digital preservation

teams. This resource aims to strengthen advocacy efforts and provide practical guidance within NSLA libraries for implementing secure and adaptable solutions for managing digital collections.

The panel recognised the need for more work to consolidate and disseminate knowledge and practical solutions. This includes the creation of introductory toolkits for communicating with IT departments, shared glossaries that bridge archival and technical terminology, and clearer guidance on sandboxing, cybersecurity standards, and risk management.

However, effectively and timely dissemination of this documentation remains a challenge. Formal publications that synthesise this information into reference form are relatively few in number, and keeping them up to date is a challenge. Other forms of shared knowledge infrastructure were discussed, like GitHub and GitBook, blogs and wikis. However, the panel was clear that while technical infrastructure can help, it can be difficult to manage and is not always reliable or suitable long term. Personal and institutional connections outlive any of these platforms.

Community networks, such as those fostered by the Digital Preservation Coalition, the Software Preservation Network, and regional groups like National and State Libraries Australasia and Australasia Preserves were highlighted as important spaces for sharing practical experiences. Such forums enable staff to compare approaches, benchmark against similar organisations, and identify common patterns across otherwise varied institutional contexts.

The panel also recognised the potential for reaching out and building connections with other 'neighbouring' communities like cybersecurity groups (such as the UK's National Cyber Security Centre) or executive forums (like the Council of Australasian University Directors of IT). Both within and beyond our digital preservation community, there is great potential in building stronger relationships by solving shared problems, together.

During the closing discussion, the panel revisited an audience question from the start of the session on communication barriers between archivists and ICT teams. "*How to Talk to IT about Digital Preservation*" [1]

was highlighted as a valuable guide for framing discussions with ICT, providing topics and questions to provide a mutual understanding of meeting digital preservation needs.

2. REFERENCES

[1] S. Prater, "How to Talk to IT about Digital Preservation," *Journal of Archival Organization*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 90–101, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1080/15332748.2018.1528827.

3. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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